

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 4.6

Demo 2: Monitoring agricultural land use and provision of value-added agricultural services II

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Short Description:
This deliverable outlines “Phase 2” pilot activities implemented within LandSense theme “Agricultural Land Use” (Demonstration Case 2), where citizens participated in acquiring and sharing agricultural in-situ data using LandSense’s CropSupport Service.
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List of Abbreviations

CDS – Change Detection Service

DC – Demonstration Case

EO – Earth Observation

LULC – Land Use Land Cover

NDVI - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Executive Summary

The LandSense Citizen Observatory (<https://landsense.eu/>) brings together the domains of citizen science and Earth Observation (EO) to address challenging issues related to in-situ monitoring in the field of Land Use and Land Cover (LULC). As part of the observatory, several technologies are being developed and deployed across three themes and various communities to illustrate the potential of citizen observatories to tackle environmental monitoring issues. This deliverable reports on the pilot activities executed within the Agricultural Land Use theme (i.e. Demonstration Case 2, Phase 2), which had been outlined in the action plan presented in Deliverable 2.3 (Engagement action plans and campaign strategies for LandSense demonstration cases II). This report outlines pilot activities implemented between February and October 2019 in Serbia, where a group of 25 farmers were actively involved in the collection of agricultural in-situ data. The data collection was facilitated by CropSupport - a LandSense technology that had been initially tested during Phase 1 campaign (D4.2), and further developed with additional important functionalities and services before the Phase 2 campaign. This deliverable will serve to feed into the D4.8: Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases - Report II.

1 Introduction

Within this pilot, the LandSense Citizen Observatory aims to facilitate the engagement of citizens in monitoring agricultural land use in Vojvodina, Serbia. The pilot activities led by INOSENS were implemented over two phases. During the Phase 1 campaign (Nov 2017-Sep 2018), the agricultural high school students and master students from University of Novi Sad had been selected as the primary targeted audience (for more details and, please see D4.2). During the Phase 2 campaign (Feb-Oct 2019), a group of individual farmers participated in the collecting of agricultural in-situ data. The implementation of this pilot brings together several key pieces of LandSense-related technology including: (i) the CropSupport mobile/web application, (ii) the Change Detection Service (CDS), (iii) the Data Quality Assurance Service (D5.2; D5.4) and (iv) the LandSense Authorization Server (D3.3).

The CropSupport application, developed by INOSENS as part of WP4, is a mobile and web-based tool for collecting in-situ data related to crop type and farm management activities. This application represents the primary tool for data collection within the DC2 activities. Besides designing the functionalities that will allow intuitive in-situ data collection, significant effort was placed on creating “added value” services that would be offered to CropSupport users in compensation for their effort and willingness to collect and share data. Namely, the application allows the users to access (free of charge) information related to their land, such as weather forecast for the micro locations of their parcels, the Change Detection Service as well as processed satellite images that contain information on potential stress of crops due to exposure to pests, plant diseases, water scarcity or nutrient elements in the soil (e.g. NDVI, vegetation and moisture indexes).

The CDS, developed by GeoVille as part of WP3 and WP4, is an application which indicate the crop status, i.e. increase/decrease of crop productivity based on a time-series analysis of Sentinel 2 satellite imagery (See D 3.4). The users access this service via CropSupport web application.

Data Quality Assurance Service, developed by UNOTT and UHEI as part of WP5 (see D5.2 and D5.4), is one out of four LandSense Services which analyses quality of data collected by the LandSense demonstrator pilot case studies. The following functionalities of this service had been tested within the DC2 campaign: data quality relating to user-captured photographs, GDPR compliance on user captured photographs, point assessment and polygon field observations.

LandSense Authorization Server, developed by SECD within WP3 (see D3.3), is part of the LandSense Engagement Platform and acts as a broker of user authentication and personal information between the Identity Providers of the LandSense Federation and the operators of registered applications and services. Each operator of registered applications and/or services can obtain a specific amount of personal information, individual for each application and service that they register. CropSupport is one among registered application on the LandSense Engagement Platform, while INOSENS represents its corresponding operator.

The following sections will provide a detailed overview of all activities and achievements accomplished within Phase 2 activities.

2 Agricultural Land Use theme in a glance - Demonstration Pilot (Serbia)

DEMONSTRATION CASE 2 (Phase 2 activities)

Monitoring Agricultural Land Use and Provision of Value-added Agricultural

The Agricultural Land Use theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added services to European farmers and public authorities in the agricultural sector. Demonstration case (Phase 2) activities were implemented in Serbia between February and October 2019.

OVERALL GOALS FOR PHASE 2 ACTIVITIES

- ✓ to demonstrate the functionalities and usefulness of CropSupport Service
- ✓ to provide a far-reaching, comprehensive monitoring and decision support tool for operational agricultural practice
- ✓ to effectively evaluate and highlight the capacities of the LandSense Citizen Observatory

SPECIFIC GOALS

- ✓ to test and validate the CropSupport application and its additional functionalities and serviced developed as a results of Phase 1 participants feedbacks in an operational setting
- ✓ to test and validate two other LandSense Services and technologies - Change Detection Service, Data Quality Assurance Service and LandSense Authorization Server
- ✓ to empower citizen-driven observations and engagement, and obtain high-quality data sets within the pilot

THE MAIN BENEFITS

- ✓ Through cutting edge IT technology, InoSens aims to help targeted individuals to acquire a better understanding of the relationship between agricultural land-use change and production. Via CropSupport Service, farmers access the useful information related to the management of daily farm activities, such as NDVI maps, CDS and weather forecast for the micro locations of their parcels.

THE MAIN UPSCALING QUALITY

- ✓ During Phase II, the CropSupport application shows a significant potential for replicability in other domains, especially in combination with other LandSense Services

To motivate farmers to actively collect agricultural in-situ data throughout the whole 2019 growing season, we had been organizing monthly visits to our citizen scientists, i.e. the farmers and their families. Each time, we went together with the farmers to visit their fields, and we did not miss the opportunity to collect in-situ data together.

Figure 1: At-a-glance of Phase 2 of the agricultural demonstration pilot in Vojvodina, Serbia.

3 Achievements

3.1 Development and testing of CropSupport application

The prototype of the CropSupport mobile and web application was developed by the end of 2017. Since then, the CropSupport application had been tested during the Phase 1 and Phase 2 activities. The user feedback collected during Phase 1 activities, guided the further improvement of the application. On the other hand, testing interoperability between CropSupport and LandSense Services and technologies (CDS, Data Quality Assurance Service and LandSense Authorization Server) has been successfully achieved within Phase 2 activities.

3.2 Demonstration of citizen science approach

The citizen science approach was demonstrated by engaging of 25 farmers from Vojvodina (northern Serbia region). Prior to the farmer engagement, the detailed plan with timeline of the pilot activities was prepared along with the supporting material (e.g. invitation letters, explanatory text & video, LandSense leaflet). Also, attention had been given to informing relevant local and regional actors about the LandSense project and the pilot activities in Serbia, where the concept of citizen science was introduced to wider community by utilizing the project communication & dissemination tools and channels.

3.3 Obtaining agricultural in-situ data

Through empowering citizen-driven observation of agricultural LULC, envisioned sets of in-situ data were obtained. Namely, the planned Phase 2's KPIs were reached, and the following data was collected: crop images, delineated crop parcels, farm management activities (e.g. crop type, seeding, tillage & harvesting date). The collected agricultural data sets will be utilized during LandSense Innovation Challenge 2 event¹ - an event that will be focused on exploiting data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory by targets individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all participating Horizon 2020 countries.

3.4 Added value service for farmers

Besides being a tool for in-situ data collection and sharing, the CropSupport application offers to its users several value-added services – such as NDVI maps, CDS, parcel-based weather forecast, farm activity diary. Most of the Phase 2 participants used EO related products for the first time, which helped them to support capacity development in the region.

¹ The 2nd LandSense Innovation Challenge event is scheduled for May 27th, 2020 in Trieste (Italy) during the Third International ECSA Conference 2020 (<https://www.ecsa-conference.eu/>)

4 Target Groups

Phase 2 activities targeted farmers as the key group for testing and validation of the improved CropSupport application and other relevant LandSense services in an operational environment. The farmer community can not only provide valuable feedback on overall performance of the CropSupport Service, but also provide important exploitation opportunities (e.g. the usefulness of the service, readiness to use this service regularly, willingness to collect and share data, etc.).

As for general motivation used to attract farmers to participate in the pilot activities, the INOSENS team promoted the acquisition of relevant and practical knowledge related to the use of the modern technology in everyday agricultural activities. Here, achieving the hands-on experience in using services such as NDVI maps, triggering CDS and benefiting from sensitive weather forecast proved to be sufficient to attract the attention of the farmers. In addition, the farmers were provided with a broad overview of citizen science and the importance of agricultural in-situ data for transforming current approaches to environmental decision making.

The most common barriers encountered during Phase 2 campaign was related to poor performance of the app on some of the farmers' smartphones (e.g. GPS device out of function, lack of memory space, etc.). On the other hand, a very tight time schedule and existence of many daily activities represent the real challenge when it comes to engagement of farmers and their active contribution in data collection. To overcome this barrier, nurturing and maintenance of close relationship with farmers were necessary.

5 Engagement strategies

The Phase 2 activities aimed to improve the uptake of the CropSupport application by the key end-user group -farmers. INOSENS teamed up with 25 committed farmers that had been guided through the collection of agricultural in-situ data over the growing season 2019. Building on awareness established during Phase 1, INOSENS reached groups of different farmers through two farmer associations (“Club of farmers Selenca” & “Center for Organic production Selenca”) as well as through its networks and connections with private companies engaged in outgrowing schemes, agricultural extension services, etc. As part of the engagement activities, the two workshops (Figures 2 & 3) were held at the beginning of the campaign, which were followed by additional engagement events:

Figure 2. Workshop 1 in Srbobran (Serbia) on February 22, 2019

Figure 3. Workshop 2 in Selenca (Serbia) on March 27, 2019

At the beginning of each workshop, the INOSENS team presented the LandSense project to farmers as well as the general objectives of the Phase 2 campaign in Serbia. After this informative part of the workshop, the team provided training on how to use the CropSupport application. After the training, only farmers that showed high interest in participating in the crowdsourcing campaign had been offered to be enrol in the pilot activities.

To sustain engagement and provide constant feedback to the users, close contact with engaged farmers was maintained during the whole campaign, including phone calls and the monthly visits of the farmers. Monthly visits to the participating farmers were made between Feb-Oct 2019 across various locations. Such engagement allowed INOSENS to create personal relationships and acquired critical feedback to further advance the CropSupport Service.

After the Phase 2 campaign had finished, INOSENS provided feedback to the all campaign participants on their contribution to overall campaign achievements and project success via a dedicated event on December 6, 2019. INOSENS co-organized a local event “Kvalitet života (*engl. Life Quality*)” that gather farmer communities among other local citizens groups (Figure 4). Here, INOSENS gave various presentations to the campaign participants, highlighting their valuable contributions and achievements.

Figure 4. Feedback event on December 6 ,2019 in Novi Sad

6 Overview of app/prototype

Within Phase 1, the prototype of the CropSupport website and mobile application was developed and tested. After Phase 1, the application had been improved in accordance with received feedback from the users and other LandSense partners (please see D4.2). In this section, the workflow of the application will be described, while the new functionalities and services will be highlighted.

6.1 Web application

The CropSupport web-based application can be found at: <https://landsense.inosens.rs>. In order to open the web-application the user needs to enter her email address and password. Once the application is opened, the main user interface appears.

Figure 5. The CropSupport web application's home page

Infobox 1. The main interface of the CropSupport web-based application

THE MAIN INTERFACE

The main interface provides access to several functions:

- (i) Google map over which user draws field parcels. The map can be zoomed in/out.
- (ii) Indication and location of photos taken via mob app (which appear on the user board).
- (iii) Possibility to outline the contours of the parcel via 'Draw Polygon' button (on the top left-hand side of the screen, beneath the 'Zoom Out' button).

FUNCTIONALITES THAT HAS BEEN DEVELOPED AFTER PHASE 1 ACTIVITIES:

- (iv) Possibility to edit shape of a parcel once it is drawn.

(v) The most recent background map over which user can precisely delineates new parcel (so it correctly responds to the current crop rotation scheme).

(vi) The Google map pinned icon that indicate direction from which the photo was taken. This situation makes it easy for a user to decide exact location of the parcel (e.g. is it on the left or right side of a road).

Infobox 2. The Parcel module of the CropSupport web-based application

PARCELS

The screenshot displays the 'My parcels' interface. On the left is a 'Parcel filter' sidebar with fields for 'Parcel name' and 'Crop type'. The main area shows three parcel cards: 'Corn (parcel 1)', 'Corn (parcel 2)', and 'Wheat (parcel 3)'. Each card includes a photo, 'Created date' (11.06.2016), 'Taken pictures' (1), 'Crop type' (/), and 'Number of activities' (0). Below each card are 'Show details' and 'Delete' buttons. Below the parcels is a weather forecast for 'Big one, KC55-5-5' for dates 20.10.2017 to 24.10.2017. It includes graphs for Temperature (16°C to 24°C), Pressure (1017 mbar to 1023 mbar), and Precipitation (0 mm). At the bottom is a 'Map index' section with a satellite map showing a red parcel boundary and a location pin.

By selecting this function, the user is opening a new screen, where a list of created parcels can be seen. Each created parcel can be edited, deleted or selected. If a certain parcel is selected, a new window provides the user with relevant information related to the parcel - weather forecast and NDVI maps. Also, this section allows users to access the “Activity timeline”, where s/he can take notes and keep records of variety of agricultural activities such as: tillage, planting, fertigation, plant protection and harvesting.

SERVICE THAT HAS BEEN DEVELOPED AFTER PHASE 1 ACTIVITIES:
 Change Detection Service - indicate the crop status, i.e. increase/decrease of crop productivity.

Infobox 3. The Image section of CropSupport web-based application

Infobox 4. The messages service of CropSupport web-based application

MESSAGES

Board
Parcels
My Images
My Messages
About
FAQ
Aleksandra Leontic @ Inosense
Log out

Post new message

Message data

Language

Message text

Go back
messagepublish.PUBLISH_TO_ADMIN

This section allows users to communicate with a CropSupport administrator in a case the user encounters technical problems. Also, this communication channel could be used for communication between campaign leader and data collectors.

Infobox 5. The “About” and “FAQ” sections of CropSupport web-based application

ABOUT, FAQ

Board
Parcels
My Images
My Messages
About
FAQ
Logout

About CropSupport

See the individual Save money and produce more!

The CropSupport digital platform provides support to farmers and other interested citizens when collecting data on land use and land cover.

For the data collection services, farmers are provided with useful information about their land through the CropSupport platform – weather forecasts for the major location of their parcels as well as processed satellite images that contain information on potential stresses due to exposure to pests, plant diseases, water scarcity or nutrient elements in the soil.

The CropSupport platform was developed by the Inosense Consulting Company from Novi Sad within the European LandSense H2020: A Citizen Observatory and the Innovation Marketplace for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring. It consists of the CropSupport web and CropSupport mobile applications. The platform represents an important step in the promotion of the concept “Citizen-observatory” that involves citizens in environmental monitoring and data collection activities, which are often the collection used for scientific purposes.

CropSupport

powered by LandSense.eu

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Board
Parcels
My Images
About
FAQ
Logout

FAQ

GENERAL

- What device do I need to use LandSense application?
- Is LandSense free for users?
- What does LandSense do to ensure privacy?

REGISTRATION

- How do I create a new LandSense account?
- How do I login to LandSense web application?
- How do I login to LandSense mobile application?
- How do I log out of my account?

THE USE OF THE LANDSENSE APP/LandSense Application Manual

- How do I use LandSense mobile app? How does LandSense work?

The “About” section allows users to obtain more information about the CropSupport application and the LandSense project. The “FAQ” section allows user to obtain information on how to use the application and all other relevant information related to the LandSense project.

6.2 Mobile application

The CropSupport mobile application can be downloaded via Google Play service following this [link](#). After installing the application, the user needs to sign-in by entering his/her email address and password.

Infobox 6. The CropSupport mobile application

DATA COLLECTION

The CropSupport mobile application is used for taking photos and entering basic information about agricultural land use (crop name; crop type). While, taking a photo of a parcel, a user must consider an “accuracy” parameter which has to be lower than 20m. User does not need access to the internet in order to take a photo. Once the mobile device is connected to Internet, photographs will be automatically synchronized with the user web application.

SERVICE THAT HAS BEEN DEVELOPED AFTER PHASE 1 ACTIVITIES:

- The possibility to enter farm activities

6.3 CropSupport application login

Prior to launching Phase 2 campaign, CropSupport was integrated with the LandSense Authorization Server. The LandSense Authorization Server is part of the LandSense Engagement Platform and acts as a broker of user authentication and personal information between the Identity Providers of the LandSense Federation and the operators of registered applications and services (for more details please D3.3). As a result, CropSupport users are asked to agree on the personal information that could be shared or not during login process.

Figure 6. CropSupport login procedure via the LandSense Authorisation Service

7 Uptake & Performance Measures

Measuring and monitoring contributions was done via the CropSupport web-based Administrator Panel, which can be used for checking validity and reliability of collected data.

Infobox 7. The “User” and “Image” sections of the Administrator panel

USERS

Via the main dashboard of the administrator panel, a particular user contribution/activity can be monitored, such as number of: parcels, images, and activities (data related to farm activities such as seeding, fertilization, irrigation, etc.). Also, the user statistics provides specific information which help assess the quality of the user data sets - number of images connected with the parcels, number of images without parcels and parcels without activities.

IMAGE VALIDITY CONTROL

The Image validity control helps for monitoring and checking validity of collected data. This service provides an opportunity for assessing the quality of collected data by enabling the administrator to compare the content of image with the user’s claim. In this way, misinterpretation of the certain land use can be reduced, and inappropriate images can be deleted, and a generic message will be sent to the user informing and explaining to him/her why the image was deleted. Also, low-quality images, where no possibility to recognised type of the crop exists (e.g. too dark or blurry images), will be deleted as well due to inability to check the validity of collected data (i.e. user claim about the crop type on the certain parcel). This service is quite important for the campaign where participants are not experts and could not easily differentiate types of crops.

Infobox 8. The “Statistic” section of the Administrator panel

STATISTIC – AGREGATED DATA

The main tool for monitoring the collected data is the “Statistics” panel which provides insights in overall performance for a defined group of users and/or for whole campaign (different schools, group of students, etc.). Same as for individual users, aggregated data on total number of parcels, images and activities is available. Also, specific information related to quality of the group data sets are shown (number of images connected with the parcels, number of images without parcels and parcels without activities).

As for in-situ data collected via CropSupport application, Phase 2 was successful and in line with the action plan outlined in D2.3. (see Table 2).

Table 1. Overview of the Phase 2 performance indicators

Metrics	Target	Achieved
Number of mobile app installs:	Not specified	100+ on Google Play
Number of registered users (web application)	Not specified	70+
Number of engaged and active users	25	25 farmers
Number of delineated parcels:	Not specified	100
Number of images:	150 +	220
Number of activities²	15 ³ +	65
Number of the CDS calls	Not specified	114

² This metric is referring to data related to the farm activities such as date of seeding, plowing, harvesting, etc.

³ This metric refers to 15 data sets, where each set will contain information for different parcels throughout the whole 2019 growing season.

8 Communication outreach

The INOSENS team recognises communication and dissemination activities are critical to the success of the project promotion and implementation of its demonstration activities as well as the exploitation of the main LandSense assets. Therefore, throughout the whole implementation period of the Phase 2 campaign, special attention was dedicated to communication of the pilot activities to the key target groups as well as to providing feedbacks on the data-collection activities to the campaign participants. To achieve this, a mixture of communication means (i.e. media and activities) were utilized:

Social media channels had been used to inform, present and engage LandSense stakeholders in corresponding pilot activities. Also, these communication channels were used to present LandSense technologies which help citizen scientists to collect and interpret in-situ data.

Figure 7. Social media announcements

Video material - in order to build relationship with the campaign participants while extending the interest in citizen science, we highlighted success moments and important information from Phase 2 campaign through a video testimonial. Namely, a short video had been created in order to share achievements and some general information related to the crowdsourcing campaign in Serbia under the LandSense project (: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FrGGsWp-OAs>).

LandSense brochure in Serbian - to increase the awareness of the LandSense project in general and importance of citizen science initiatives, the INOSENS team translated the LandSense project brochure from English to Serbian. The LandSense brochure translated in Serbian and designed to portray the main project ideas and objectives, helped to spur interest of wider audience to our project and activities.

Figure 9. LandSense brochure in Serbian

CropSupport one-pager – INOSENS designed a one-page flyer that provides the most important information about CropSupport application. This marketing material is widely used during *offline* dissemination activities (please see below “Offline events”), where the campaign results and exploitation potential of this LandSense technology were promoted. This document will be further utilized during the upcoming exploitation activities within WP6.

Crop Support

<https://www.facebook.com/pg/CropSupport/>
Eu Project: Landesense - A Citizen Observatory and the Innovation Marketplace for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring (689812).

Established: Late 2017
Number of Users: 100

The CropSupport application provides support to farmers and other interested citizens when collecting data on land use and land cover. It consists of the CropSupport web and CropSupport Android applications. The platform represents an important step in the promotion of the concept “citizen observatory” that involves citizens in environmental monitoring and data collection activities, which are after the collection used for scientific purposes.

The CropSupport web-based application is an interactive platform that can be accessed once users register for an account. The main functionalities of the web application are:

- o Possibility to outline the contours of a field parcel over a base layer imagery from Google
- o Indication and location of photos taken via mobile app (which appear on the user board)
- o Parcel profile - allows user to acquire different information related to the parcel - weather forecast and NDVI maps. Also, this section allows user to access to “Activity timeline”, where s/he can take notes and keep records of variety of agricultural activities such as: tillage, planting, fertigation, plant protection and harvesting
- o Communication channel for communication with campaign leader

The CropSupport mobile application is used for taking photos and entering basic information about agricultural land use (crop name; crop type). While, taking a photo of a parcel, a user must consider “accuracy” parameter which has to be below 20m. User does not need access to the internet in order to take a photo. Once the mobile device is connected to Internet, taken images will be automatically synchronized with the user web application. Currently, the mob application is available only for “Android” devices.

The Administrator Panel is an extension of the CropSupport web application, and it was developed to support monitoring of the crowdsourcing campaigns (i.e. users’ commitments and quality of collected data). In particular, via the main dashboard of the Administration Panel, a particular user contribution/activity can be monitored, such as number of: parcels, images, and activities (data related to farm activities such as seeding, fertilization, irrigation, etc.). Also, the user statistic provides specific information which help assess the quality of the user data sets - number of images connected with the parcels, number of images without parcels and parcels without activities. The Image Validity Control helps for monitoring and checking the collected data. In particular, this service enables the administrator to compare the content of image with the user’s claim. Statistics panel provides insights of overall performance for defined group of users and/or for whole campaign (different schools, group of students, etc.). Same as for individual users, aggregated data on total number of parcels, images and activities is available.

About Us

Founded in 2014, in Novi Sad, Serbia, InoSens is an innovation driven consultancy focused on value creation in the agrifood value chain.

We are actively engaged in pan-European Horizon2020 Projects, as well as in consulting with companies in both Europe and the Middle-East on implementing precision agriculture technology and sustainable agricultural business models. Moreover, InoSens has a keen understanding in many critical agricultural issues and challenges farmers face when seeking to grow and elevate their farming performances.

European Commission

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Figure 10. CropSupport one-pager

Agricultural Land Use theme and CropSupport poster – to support presentation of the Agricultural land use pilot, as well as the CropSupport service at various events, the INOSENS team prepared poster. Among other events, the poster had been presented during Living Planet Symposium 2019 (May 2019, Milano, Italy) and the public event “Kvalitet života” (Dec 2019, Novi Sad, Serbia). There are two versions of the poster – in English and Serbian language.

LandSense
A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

INOSENS

CropSupport – nova alatka za prikupljanje podataka o poljoprivrednoj proizvodnji

LandSense
A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

U okviru međunarodnog projekta „LandSense“ se razvija inovativna opservatorija za monitoring upotrebe zemljišta i zemljišnog pokrivača. Za rad ove opservatorije se koriste satelitski snimci i in-situ podaci sakupljeni od strane građana. Samim tim, LandSense projekat testira da ukazuje na veliki potencijal nauka u kojoj zainteresovani građani imaju aktivan doprinos u sakupljanju podataka, a koji se potom koriste kao dopuna satelitskim podacima. Kao takav, projekat doprinosi unapređenju načina na koji vidimo, naprimo i razumemo svet oko sebe.

CropSupport

NOVI POGLED NA USEVE

ŠTA JE CROPSUPPORT APLIKACIJA?
CropSupport aplikacija podržava uključivanje građana u sakupljanje podataka o upotrebi poljoprivrednog zemljišta. Ova alatka je razvijena unutar evropskog “H2020” projekta – LandSense.

ZA ŠTA SE KORISTI APLIKACIJA?
CropSupport je alatka sačinjena od web i mobilne aplikacije. Aplikacija omogućava poljoprivrednicima sakupljanje podataka o načinu korišćenja zemljišta kao i vodjenja evidencije o svojim dnevnim aktivnostima. CropSupport aplikacija nudi nekoliko besplatnih servisa svojim korisnicima – kao što su NDVI mape, precizna vremenska prognoza, servis za detekciju promena, i dnevnik poljoprivrednih aktivnosti.

CROPSUPPORT MOBILNA APLIKACIJA

1) Korisnik može da napravi fotografiju

Prilikom fotografisanja, mobilna aplikacija korisnika može da pretraži satelitski snimke posebnosti kao što su: da li su toba, i opad. 20m. Sa druge strane, prilikom fotografisanja, aplikacija korisnika ne mora da bude povezana na internet mrežu. Kada se aplikacija koristi na internetu, aplikacija će se automatski sinhronizovati sa veb aplikacijom.

2) Korisnik može uneti osnovne informacije o načinu korišćenja zemljišta (tip i naziv useva)

CROPSUPPORT VEB APLIKACIJA

1) Glavni korisnički prozor aplikacije obezbeđuje pristup ka nekoliko servisa:

- Dinamičnu mapu preko koje korisnik ucrtava poljoprivredne parcele
- Indikator lokacije na kojima su napravljene fotografije putem mobilne aplikacije
- Mogućnost ucrtavanja kontura poljoprivrednih parcela (tj. njiva)

2) Dodatni servisi:

- Precizna vremenska prognoza
- NDVI* mape
- Servis detekcije promena

* engl. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (normalizovana razlika indeksa vegetacije)

CropSupport aplikacija je testirana i validirana sa grupom korisnika u periodu od 2017. do 2019. godine. U ovom aktivnostima je učestvovala grupa od 60 učenika dve srednje poljoprivredne škole iz Rume i Bača tokom 2017. i 2018. godine, kao i grupa studenata sa Prirodno matematičkog fakulteta u Novom Sadu. Tokom 2019. godine, aplikaciju je testirala grupa od 25 poljoprivrednika. Preliminarni rezultati analize korišćenja aplikacije ukazuju da postoji solidan potencijal za masovno korišćenje aplikacije kako u Srbiji tako i u drugim evropskim zemljama.

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Sredstva za projekat LandSense su obezbeđena od strane Evropske Unije u sklopu Programa za istraživanje i inovacija sa brojem ugovora 688612.

Figure 11. CropsSupport poster (in Serbian)

Offline events – the INOSENS team leveraged existing networks to gauge the key stakeholder interests and generate demand for LandSense in general, and CropSupport service in particular. Here, we present the LandSense project and CropSupport Service to different stakeholders as well as user groups outside of the project that can make concrete use of the project results and CropSupport Service through scientific, economic or societal exploitation. We would like to highlight the following events:

- University of Würzburg, Germany (May 2019) - presentation of LandSense project and CropSupport application to a group of biodiversity protection and land mapping researchers.
- University of Lund, Sweden (July 2019) – overview of the LandSense project and presentation of CropSupport application and its use within the Agricultural Land Use Theme to the group of representatives of the European leading research institutions and centers of water and soil research.
- ICTurkey H2020 Istanbul, Turkey (July 2019) – promotion of exploitable aspects of LandSense project and CropSupport Service through B2B meeting with over 20 different institution and organisations from all over Europe and Turkey.

Figure 12. Impressions from LandSense/CropSupport presentations at the University of Würzburg, University of Lund and at ICTurkey H2020 Istanbul event

9 Challenges

During the regular meeting and monthly visits organised during the Phase 2, the end users reported their experiences of being involved in a citizen science and using the CropSupport application and other LandSense services and technologies. The participants feedback is presented below, which will serve as input for D4.8 Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases - Report II:

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE USER ENGAGEMENT:

- Specific timetable of farmers activities (very tight time schedule during the season and not so much time available for side activities);
- Outdated mobile devices with poor hardware and software performance.

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE USE OF CROPSUPPORT WEB AND MOBILE APPLICATION

- The users did not report any specific challenge related to existing functionalities of CropSupport application (all challenges reported in D4.2 had been successfully addressed prior to Phase 2 activities).

CHALLENGES RELATED TO THE CDS

- As many of the Serbian individual farmers own rather narrow crop parcels – with usual width of 50m, many of the Phase 2 campaign participants could not obtain useful data from this service (therefore, to utilize this service to full extent, the CDS should be rather used for monitoring of wider parcels).

10 Next steps

The involvement of the citizens in agricultural data collection will provide valuable insights and inputs for exploitation activities (WP6), where significant effort will be directed towards reaching our targeted audience that can make tangible use of the project’s campaign outcomes, services and technologies. For example, the results of the campaign will be directly utilized during the LandSense Innovation Challenge event during the 3rd ECSA conference 2020 (Trieste, Italy), where the LandSense team will facilitate collaboration and innovation among stakeholders within the value chain related to land mapping and citizen science. Here, targeted individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs will be invited to present innovative IT solutions addressing one of the three LandSense domains by exploiting data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory. Also, the in-situ data collected within the agricultural campaign will be utilized by other project partners who have been engaged in developing and testing of other LandSense services and technologies (i.e. quality evaluation of citizen-observed data (D5.6) and impact/sustainability assessments (D2.4)).

As for the CropSupport Service and its future use, the WP6 team has started to target relevant audience and areas where this technology could be exploited. To this end, we have outlined an initial exploitation strategy, where the preliminary business canvas model defines the key elements such as value proposition, infrastructure, customers, and finances (for details please see D6.4). Also, the following areas where CropSupport could be exploited in post-project period have been identified: crop insurance, agricultural water management, biodiversity monitoring, future European funded projects, etc. In the coming period, this list will be refined where the exploitation and business strategy will be precisely defined in the upcoming deliverables D6.7 and D6.9. In particular, the following activities related to the CropSupport Service exploitation and IP issues are envisioned:

- Updating the exploitation plan outlined within D6.4 (Exploitation and IP management strategies I);
- Defining the IP rights in the agreement and cooperation with the other project partners;
- Defining the business plans for CropSupport Service targeting niche markets for LULC monitoring activities (D6.9);
- Active dissemination of the LandSense agricultural theme achievements and results.